

2-TOM, 1-SON
THE ROLE OF HUMAN PSYCHOLOGY IN LEARNING
LANGUAGES.

Mamarasulova Durdona Feruz qizi
Uzbekistan Foreign Languages University

Abstract. Psychological aspects of the process of learning a foreign language are presented in the article will be considered. The role of psychology in education and its pedagogy and linguistics learns the connection with Psychological theories in teaching foreign languages in the article methods of application, professional language competence of the teacher, educational subject and factors taking into account the individual characteristics of students, especially foreign languages emphasizes the importance of learning motivation. This article is the main topic of education psychological-pedagogical analysis with its factors and components is given. In the article The definition of pedagogical psychology is close to its development and youth psychology connection is given. The main parts of pedagogical psychology are defined and the importance of pedagogical psychology in the teaching process and foreign language acquisition role is shown.

Key words: professional language competence, study motivation, individual characteristics, psychological approach.

It is difficult to overestimate the meaning of a foreign language for modern society as it influences directly all the main life aspects in the development of every country. Nowadays, to be a highly qualified specialist signifies not only to be professional in your narrow sphere of knowledge but to master foreign languages as well. There exist different factors in providing successful foreign language teaching. One of the most important among them belongs to Psychology. Deep understanding of various psychological aspects may help teachers to solve many key moments in their work: to find a proper method of working in every students' group; to realize the right approach to students according to their skills and abilities taking into account complicated age peculiarities; to provide high motivation in foreign language mastering; to overcome natural problems, so called "barriers" appearing in the process of language studying. For getting good knowledge of any language, either foreign or native, everybody should be acquainted with Psychology – the discipline that is closely connected with language teaching. According to the studied literature, many prominent scientists were interested in psychological side of Pedagogy trying to make the process of education more effective. Thus, J. Manesca, H. G. Ollendorff, H. Sweet, H. Palmer tried to apply psychological theories in their language teaching principles and

2-TOM, 1-SON

approaches. I. V. Rahmanov was one of the leading researchers in the history of methods of teaching foreign languages

At the same time, it has been repeatedly pointed out that many people learn English, but only a few know it well. The language is good in modern conditions non-linguistic despite the universally recognized importance of teaching. There is a lot of educated people who speak English well in our country not a frequent occurrence. Educational psychology is the study of how people learn in educational settings. The effectiveness of educational activities, the psychology of teaching and as an organization studies the social psychology of schools. Educational psychology of students deals with how to learn and develop, often gifted children and focuses on subgroups with specific disabilities. For a deeper understanding of educational psychology, its interaction with other disciplines it is better to check the connection properly. Much of the information comes from Psychology, but it in turn enriches many other fields of science. Educational psychology draws from and contributes to cognitive science and learning. Each teacher to better understand the abilities of students with its distinguishing features, individuality, not only in adulthood, but also we believe that he should get acquainted even in childhood. For this purpose, pedagogical psychology develops and applies theories of human development. Here they are very important, because their main goal is all changes in mental abilities, knowledge is an examination of moral reasoning about nature . Considering all this, the problem of learning English is only didactic understanding seems insufficient. It affects the process, but it is necessary to pay more attention to the factors that lie outside of linguodidactics. The most important of them is psychological, and in this article we will discuss their purely methodological we show the connection with aspects. Among the main psychological aspects of learning English, they are the most important are: motivation and interest in language learning; language learning ability; the ratio of language and speech in learning; language barrier. Motivation is the main factor in language learning. In any activity as it is, if a person does not want to do something or does it by force, he cannot achieve a high result. The only result in language learning is success can provide motivation for To avoid failure motivation can give one-time results. For example, a student is demanding English afraid of failing the exam with the language teacher. He is from the exam will pass, maybe not bad, but such local success is long-term will have no effect.

Despite the obviousness of the above arguments, many people speak English well although he has started learning, he still does not follow it. Why are they? lose

2-TOM, 1-SON

motivation? The point is that English is, for example, a computer system unlike mastering or learning to drive a car, it is continuous and systematic it needs to be practiced and many people are not ready for it. Mostly, some Circumstances prevent him from doing this and he becomes a convenient reason, an excuse. This requires certain voluntary actions that have not been taken into account. English language skills Another feature of quality is that it seems unnecessary in everyday life. In fact, if all the information is in Russian, if you are your native language if you are in the environment and feel comfortable in it, it is artificial for you. It takes strong willpower to create a foreign language environment. On the other hand, many learned English without going to countries where it is the official language and it cannot be said that they have any superpowers. English is known as an international language and is used as an international communication tool. Language is the only way of communication, even before the formation of human societies; people interacted together by engraving on the stones and walls. The learning of mother language is very important, but don't forget it if somebody doesn't learn an international language (English), they face many serious problems because technology and science are rapidly developing in the English language [10, 44]. The purpose of this paper is to encourage the teachers to help the learner's speaking skills in English classes with the educational knowledge. There are several major problems related to lack of communication in the English class. Not only the teacher provides the student's mental condition and reduces their anxiety in the class, creating a comfortable atmosphere in the classroom and also motivates the learners, but the teacher should choose a teaching approach that isn't boring for students. The teachers should choose objectives that the students can realize within the parameters of the course activities and assignments [5, 14]. Language students should understand that the teacher expects them to be able to use the material they are learning to speak to someone else. They should also know that the teacher expects them to participate in the foreign language in the class activities. Between the skills in learning English language, speaking plays several roles in language learning in the class. One of the most important roles of speaking is to serve as a vehicle for participating in class activities and also one of the greatest challenges facing language teachers is that of creating new and more productive ways to help students develop communication skills. Vocabulary is an indispensable part of the English language learning process. It would be impossible to learn a language without vocabulary. It is the primary skill which should be mastered by the children before they acquire another language skill, such as listening, speaking, reading, and writing. It means that vocabulary plays an important

2-TOM, 1-SON

role in both spoken and written communication. The next step in the process of successful language acquisition is for students attracts attention. Better presentation of material and it by students. The teacher also needs to focus on the process and the given lesson getting acquainted with the psychological theory related to the process of mastering the material need In addition, it is very important for every teacher to keep students focused is important. For this, the teacher uses different teaching methods. So, using a visual aid at the right time is a big help in this case will give. The teacher does not lose the attention of the students after a few minutes should take care of. It is very important to use visual aids on time, etc otherwise, the effect will be completely opposite. For example, a picture hanging in front of the class at the beginning of the lesson or any table will not have a positive effect because the students have already seen it and their attention is not concentrated at the same time. In this case, visual aid not using it on time can have negative effects.

Conclusions Most learners would like to learn to speak the English language, but developing speaking skills isn't easy. They attempt to learn this language as a foreign language that's why they looking for the best teacher who teaches them the English language in an appropriate class. Teaching English in a variety of countries, including Iran, faces many problems. Most teachers and students involved in the teaching learning process many hours in the class, but they haven't had much success. Which is why the researcher in this paper highlights the usage of psychology along with teaching? Every teacher should have complete knowledge of educational psychology so that helps to the learners in learning a foreign language. Understanding and identifying the desire, motivation, mental, and physical of the learners can help them learn more. According this hypothesis teacher identified the character of various students then begins teaching. She selected the PowerPoint style to teach English vocabulary to them, the aim of this method is to attract the learner's motivation and use of group activities helped to reduce their anxiety in class. The skillful teacher entered the shy children into the conversation and improved self-confidence of other learners in speaking skills of English language class. Therefore, the teacher's success is a fundamental principle and the attention of all teachers to the use of educational and behavioral methods should be prioritized.

2-TOM, 1-SON

References

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